

An Interdependent Model of Personality, Motivation, Emotion, and Mood for Intelligent Virtual Agents

1 EMPIRICALLY BASED MAPPINGS

In this section we will list the various mappings between the components of our proposed model of affect, i.e. between personality, motivation, emotions, and mood.

1.1 Mood Discretization

As discussed in Section 4.4, the current mood $\mathbf{b} \in B$ of the agent is modeled as a continuous point in the three dimensional PAD space. Just as each dimension in this space is tied to a specific meaning, the octants are also assigned specific interpretations, cf. Table 1.

We use this discretization (\mathbf{b}) as a proxy for deciding when the mood can influence the intensity of an experienced emotion (see Equation (7) in the main text). Note that the described mechanism is more general than this particular discretization, such that another distance measures could be used for the increase or decrease of the baseline intensity (e.g. simple euclidean distance or angular distance in the PAD space between the emotion and mood).

Table 1: Mood octants in the PAD space, adapted from [2].

P	A	D	label	P	A	D	label
+	+	+	Exuberant	-	-	-	Bored
+	+	-	Dependent	-	-	+	Disdainful
+	-	+	Relaxed	-	+	-	Anxious
+	-	-	Docile	-	+	+	Hostile

1.2 Mapping: Personality \Rightarrow Motivation

As discussed in Section 5.1, we base the influence of personality on motivation on a body of work which has shown a correlation between a person’s personality traits and the importance they assign to each motivation [1, 6]. Table 2 presents a mapping between each of Reiss’ 16 motivations and the FFM traits, based on the statistically significant findings of [6].

Also as is mentioned, we reflect this correlation in the weight vector \mathbf{w} that is used by the heuristic search in Equation (1) to weight the individual motivational dimensions. Note that previous work has not used this empirically based mapping between Reiss’ 16 basic desires and the FFM personality traits. Since research suggests that personality and motivation do not seem to map onto one another such that only one of the two can be used to model both [6]; therefore, there is merit to modeling both the agent’s personality and its motivations, while weighting the agent’s motivational profile according to the empirically based correlations found between the two constructs. Since this mechanism models the general notion that an individual’s personality influences the way in which they assign importance to the different motivations, different theories of personality and motivation can, theoretically, be used.

Table 2: Mapping between Reiss’ 16 basic desires and the FFM traits based on the statistically significant findings of [6]. (-) signifies no correlation between the motivation and the FFM trait.

Motivation	O	C	E	A	N
Acceptance	-	-	-	-	0.5
Curiosity	0.46	-	-	-	-
Eating	-	-	-	-	0.25
Family	-	0.21	-	0.22	-
Honor	-	0.31	-	0.18	-
Idealism	0.17	0.24	-	0.3	-
Independence	-	-	-	-0.29	-
Order	-0.19	-	-	-	0.33
Physical Activity	0.17	0.24	-	0.3	-
Power	-	-	0.39	-0.18	-
Romance	-	-	-	-0.23	-
Saving	-	-	-	-0.16	0.28
Social Contact	0.2	-	0.58	-	-
Social Status	-	-	0.19	-0.28	0.24
Tranquility	-	-	-	-	0.46
Vengeance	-	0.28	-	-0.61	0.31

1.3 Mapping: Emotion \Rightarrow Mood

As discussed in Section 5.2, the mood B is modeled in PAD space and the emotions E are represented by the OCC emotion types. Thus, we use a correspondence between the OCC emotions and the PAD space (taken from [5]). Table 3 presents this mapping $\phi(e_i) : E \rightarrow B$ between the OCC emotion types e_i and their PAD space coordinates.

We use this mapping to represent all active emotions in PAD space, combine them to compute an effective mood $\mathbf{b}_t^{\text{eff}}$, which, in turn, is used at each time step t to ‘pull’ on the current mood \mathbf{b}_t (see Equation (3) in the main text). Note that this general mechanism captures this empirically-based definition of mood: “an average of a person’s emotional states across a representative variety of life situations” [4]. Thus, a different representation of mood and emotion can be used, as long as a correlation between the two is established.

1.4 Mapping: Personality \Rightarrow Emotion

As discussed in Section 5.3, we model the empirically-based notion that an individual’s personality can up or down regulate emotions [3]. For example, individuals who have a high neuroticism value will experience negative emotions more intensely [3]. Table 3 presents a correlation between each of the FFM personality traits and the OCC emotion types, based on [3]. In our model, this correlation $\chi(p, e) : P \times E \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ is used in Equation (8) to modulate the intensity of an experienced emotion. Once again, this relation captures a general empirically-based mechanism which is evident in human beings; thus, alternative theories of emotion can easily be used instead of the OCC.

Table 3: A mapping between the OCC emotion types and the FFM traits. (+) and (-) signify, respectively, that the personality trait increases or decreases the emotion’s intensity upon elicitation. An empty cell signifies no effect. Additionally, the mapping of OCC emotion types into PAD space is shown (adapted from ALMA [2]).

Emotion	O	C	E	A	N	P	A	D
Joy	+		+			0.4	0.2	0.1
Distress	+				+	-0.4	-0.2	-0.5
Resentment	+	+		-	+	-0.2	-0.3	-0.2
Pity	+			+	+	-0.4	-0.2	-0.5
Hope			+			0.2	0.2	-0.1
Fear	-	+			+	-0.64	0.60	-0.43
Satisfaction	+		+			0.3	-0.2	0.4
Relief			+			0.2	-0.3	0.4
Disappointment	-				+	-0.3	0.1	-0.4
Pride	+		+			0.4	0.3	0.3
Admiration	+		+	+		0.5	0.3	-0.2
Shame	-				+	-0.3	0.1	-0.6
Reproach				-	+	-0.3	-0.1	0.4
Liking	+		+	+		0.4	0.16	-0.24
Disliking				-	+	-0.4	0.2	0.1
Gratitude	+		+			0.4	0.2	-0.3
Anger				-	+	-0.51	0.59	0.25
Gratification	+		+			0.6	0.5	0.4
Remorse	+				+	-0.3	0.1	-0.6
Love	+		+			0.3	0.1	0.2
Hate	+			-	+	-0.6	0.6	0.3

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